

Short communication

Measles virus infection: a snapshot from N. Greece in 2017

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Summary

Measles is an infectious disease that still represents an existing health issue of concern in Europe. While the World Health Organization (WHO) target for the elimination of measles virus has been postponed until year 2020, in 2016 measles outbreaks were seen in a number of EU/EEA countries and an increase in the number of cases is still observed in 2017, some linked to the large ongoing outbreak in Romania. Since 2010, there has been no report from outbreaks in Greece. However, sporadic cases are reported and genotyping of a recent case with no known travel history, revealed a B3 genotype, similarly to other parts of the WHO European region, Austria, Belgium, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Portugal, Sweden, UK and also Romania. National policies need to assure increased routine vaccination uptake of hard-to-reach groups, especially taking under consideration the large immigrant wave in the region. It is essential to continue epidemiological and virological surveillance of measles in Greece to monitor the transmission pattern of the virus and the effectiveness of measles immunization, which will eventually lead to the achievement of the goal for elimination.

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Key words

measles, Greece, genotyping, virological surveillance

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The recent measles outbreaks in Europe emphasise that this infectious disease still represents a health issue of concern that is existing in Europe. Despite a large decline in measles incidence in the past decade in Europe, the World Health Organization (WHO) target for the elimination of measles virus (MV) to at least five WHO regions, has been postponed until year 2020^{1,2}. Measles virus is still present in Europe, causing severe disease with complications and high fatality rates in children². The European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) has recently published a rapid risk assessment, reporting that in 2016 measles outbreaks were seen in a number of EU/EEA countries and an increase in the number of cases is still observed in 2017². As of March 2017, previous and ongoing measles outbreaks in three EU countries have been epidemiologically linked to a current outbreak in Romania².

Measles is a notifiable disease in Greece and the European Union (EU) case definition of 2008 is used³. Overall, measles incidence has been steadily declining in Greece during the past 25 years and the last measles outbreaks occurred in Greece in 1996, 2005 and 2006 and lastly in 2010⁴. The 2-5-year measles epidemic cycles previously observed ended after the 1996 measles outbreak⁴.

The most recent epidemic in 2010 was originally related to an outbreak in Bulgaria. Viruses belonging to the D4 genotype (group 4) were circulating among the Roma population of Bulgarian nationality, the Greek Roma population and Greek non-minority individuals^{4,5}. Cases were mostly unvaccinated children aged 0-14 years⁶. During the 2005-2006 outbreak, a D6 genotype virus was circulating^{7,8}. The past outbreak, in 2005-2006, had mainly affected unvaccinated Roma children aged 0-14 years⁴. Older teenagers and young adults from the non-minority general population or all-age immigrants who were either unvaccinated or incompletely vaccinated were also affected⁴. Following these epidemics, measures were taken to raise clinical awareness, and vaccination of specific population groups commenced. Overall, during 2004-2014 in Greece, transmission has been higher in the 0-4 year old age group with 5,43 cases/100,000 population, while in the general population cases were calculated to be 0,65/100,000⁴.

The high proportion of Greek nationals, mainly from Roma communities, during the previous outbreaks underlined that despite the high national immunisation coverage with measles-mumps-rubella

(MMR) vaccine, pockets of unvaccinated populations still exist. Vaccination with two doses of MMR vaccine has been included in the national immunisation schedule in Greece since 1991. According to the national immunisation schedule, vaccination with the first dose of MMR is recommended at the age of 12-15 months and with the second dose at the age of 4-6 years. Immunisation coverage with MMR is high in children in Greece, but less than optimal in adolescents and young adults. In some population groups (e.g. Greek Roma) vaccination coverage is low⁶. Based on the ECDC report, the vaccination coverage in many EU/EEA countries also remains suboptimal². Considering the extend of the current outbreak in Romania and the fact that the vaccination coverage in Romania is below 90%, there is a high risk of continued measles transmission within the country that in turn poses a risk of potential repeated exportation to other EU/EEA countries and possible continuous transmission in countries where vaccination coverage is suboptimal².

Since 2010, there has been no report from outbreaks in Greece and it is considered among the EU/EEA Member States that have interrupted endemic transmission for between 24 and 35 months². Sporadic cases are reported and genotyping of a recent northern Greek virus strain of an elderly patient of Greek nationality, without known travel history, presented with Influenza-Like-Illness (ILI) was performed. MV was detected by real time RT-PCR and the 447-bp segment of the nucleoprotein (N) gene was used for genotyping. The N gene sequence of the MV strain showed that it belonged to the B3 genotype similarly to recently reported strains from other parts of the WHO European region, Austria, Belgium, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Portugal, Sweden, UK and also Romania². A phylogenetic tree was constructed using recent representative MV strains from the WHO European region, recent and older Greek strains and the vaccine strain (Figure 1).

It is essential to continue epidemiological and virological surveillance of measles in Greece to monitor the transmission pattern of the virus and the effectiveness of measles immunization, which will eventually lead to the achievement of the goal for elimination. Consideration of potential under-reporting of cases is an important aspect for effectively monitoring MV circulation. National policies need to assure increased routine vaccination uptake of hard-to-reach groups, especially taking under consideration the large immigrant wave in the region.

Figure 1

Phylogenetic relationships based on 447-nt region between the Greek measles strains and other currently reported measles strains from European countries. The evolutionary history was inferred by using the Maximum Likelihood method based on the Jukes-Cantor model. The tree with the highest log likelihood is shown. Initial tree(s) for the heuristic search were obtained automatically by applying Neighbor-Join and BioNJ algorithms to a matrix of pairwise distances estimated using the Maximum Composite Likelihood (MCL) approach, and then selecting the topology with superior log likelihood value. The tree is drawn to scale, with branch lengths measured in the number of substitutions per site. Evolutionary analyses were conducted in MEGA7¹⁰.

Περίληψη

Η νόσος της ιλαράς στη Βόρεια Ελλάδα, 2017

Αγγελική Μελίδου, Γεωργία Γκιούλα, Μαρία Εξηντάρη

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Η νόσος της ιλαράς εξακολουθεί να αποτελεί απειλή για τη δημόσια υγεία. Ενώ ο Παγκόσμιος Οργανισμός Υγείας (Π.Ο.Υ.) έχει θέσει ως στόχο για την εξάλειψη της νόσου το έτος 2020, το 2016 επιδημίες ιλαράς αναφέρθηκαν σε χώρες της Ευρώπης και αύξηση στον αριθμό των κρουσμάτων παρατηρήθηκε το 2017. Από το 2010, δεν υπάρχει αναφορά για επιδημία ιλαράς στην Ελλάδα. Γονοτύπηση ενός μεμονωμένου περιστατικού στη Βόρεια Ελλάδα έδειξε ότι το στέλεχος ιλαράς ανήκε στον γονότυπο Β3, όπως και σε άλλες περιοχές της Ευρώπης: Αυστρία, Βέλγιο, Γερμανία, Ιρλανδία, Ιταλία, Πορτογαλία, Σουηδία, Μεγάλη Βρετανία και στη Ρουμανία. Είναι σημαντικό να συνεχισθεί η επιδημιολογική και ιολογική επιτήρηση του ιού της ιλαράς στην Ελλάδα και η εθνική πολιτική εμβολιασμού να συμπεριλάβει το μεγάλο κύμα προσφύγων στην περιοχή. Με την συνεχή επιτήρηση θα παρακολουθείται η πορεία μετάδοσης του ιού και η αποτελεσματικότητα της εθνικής πολιτικής εμβολιασμού, με τελικό στόχο την εξάλειψη της νόσου στην Ελλάδα και παγκοσμίως.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

ιλαρά, Ελλάδα, γονοτύπηση, ιολογική επιτήρηση

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